

Coordination chemistry at the turn of the century[†]

George B. Kauffman

Department of Chemistry, California State University, Fresno, CA 93740-8024, USA

E-mail : georgek@csufresno.edu

This historical overview is confined to the major discoveries in coordination chemistry, both experimental and theoretical, in the evolution of the discipline, and many interesting but minor events must necessarily be omitted. It is illustrative and selective rather than exhaustive, and I have had to omit many worthy contributions. Because earlier, more temporally distant works are probably less well known to you than are later works that are related more directly to your work, I shall deal with them in greater detail. Also, because science advances by eliminating errors, I have included a few unsuccessful Contributions. Furthermore, in keeping with my own interests, I have emphasized stereochemical contributions. I have included the countries of origin of some of the contributors to emphasize the international nature of science and of this conference. Werner's monumental achievements occupied a central role and dominated the first decades of the century. Even today they are still the basis for the latest developments. Therefore I shall treat his contributions in some depth.

Introduction

When my instructor Louis C. W. Baker aroused my interest in coordination chemistry during my first year as a student at the University of Pennsylvania in 1948, my only guide to the field was a slim, 82-page volume¹. Following the publication of the first general monograph in English on coordination chemistry by John C. Bailar, Jr. and his students in 1956², books on the field in general and on its specialized aspects have appeared in print in increasing numbers³. Thus, during the half-century of my acquaintance with coordination chemistry, I have watched with great satisfaction as it grew from a highly specialized area of inorganic chemistry (which itself languished in the doldrums until what Ronald S. Nyholm called the Renaissance in Inorganic Chemistry occurred following World War II) into one of the most active and productive fields of chemistry today.

As we stand at the threshold of a new century, it may be instructive to look back at past achievements in coordination chemistry. While I would not agree completely with American orator Patrick Henry's statement, "I have no way of judging of the future but by the past", I would agree with Shakespeare's more familiar maxim, "What is past is prologue". As we celebrate the turn of the century, we may discern some glimpses of the future of our field by examining its past.

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Werner's coordination theory

Because sufficient experimental data must be accumulated before attempts are made to explain these experimental facts and to predict new phenomena, theory in science usually lags behind practice. During the first half of the nineteenth century, discoveries of coordination compounds were few, sporadic, and often accidental. Therefore we might expect that few theories of coordination compounds were proposed until late in the second half of the nineteenth century. This was not so in coordination chemistry. The lag of theory behind practice was not great because of the tremendous importance of coordination compounds to the general problem of chemical bonding.

In 1893 Alfred Werner (1866-1919)^{9,10} challenged all previous theories, especially the reigning chain theory¹¹,

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proposed by the Swede Christian Wilhelm Blomstrand (1826-1897)¹² as developed and experimentally advanced by the Dane Sophus Mads Jørgensen (1837-1914)¹³, with a revolutionary new theory¹⁴. According to Werner's own admission, it was based on Jørgensen's painstaking experimental data. In fact, Jørgensen's work bore the seeds of the chain theory's destruction; some of Jørgensen's compounds later were crucial in Werner's proof of his coordination theory¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

Werner's theory abruptly broke with classical theories of valence and structure, postulating two types of valence – primary of ionizable valence (*Hauptvalenz*) and secondary or nonionizable valence (*Nebenvaleanz*). Every metal in a given oxidation state (primary valence) also has a fixed coordination number (a specific number of secondary valences that must be satisfied). Primary valences can be satisfied only by anions, but secondary valences can be satisfied by anions and neutral molecules. Secondary valences are directed in space around the central metal atom. The combined aggregate forms a "complex", which usually exists as a discrete unit in solution. The commonest configurations are octahedral (coordination number six) and square-planar or tetrahedral (coordination number four). Werner's view of the two types of linkages – "ionogenic" (ionizable) and "nonionogenic" (nonionizable) – clarified ideas of chemical bonding a generation before Kossel's and Lewis's views (1916) led to present concepts of ionic and covalent bonding, respectively.

Although the conductance studies^{18,19} of Werner with his former fellow student, the Italian chemist Arturo Miolati (1869 -1956)²⁰, conclusively settled the question of the *constitution* of coordination compounds, as the twentieth century began the question of the *configuration* of these compounds had not been conclusively settled. The technique of "isomer counting" used by Werner to prove the configuration of cobalt-ammines and other complexes did not originate with him, but had been used earlier by Wilhelm Körner for benzene derivatives in 1874 and was suggested by Jacobus Henricus van't Hoff in 1875. However, the technique of comparing the number and type of isomers *actually prepared* with the number and type *theoretically predicted* for different configurations probably attained its zenith with Werner. Not only did he use this method to discredit completely the chain theory but also to demonstrate unequivocally an octahedral configuration for cobalt(III) rather than another symmetrical arrangement, e.g. hexagonal planar or trigonal prismatic.

Geometric isomerism : Werner and his students prepared and characterized, in most cases for the first time, geomet-

ric isomers of 53 series of cobalt and chromium complexes²¹. In most cases the number and type of isomers prepared agreed with the expectations for the octahedral configuration. However, there were a few exceptions ; it took Werner more than twenty years to accumulate a definitive proof for his structural ideas. For example, the best known case of geometric (*cis-trans*) isomerism was observed by Jørgensen not among simple tetraammines MA_4B_2 but among salts $M(AA)_2B_2$, in which the four ammonia molecules had been replaced by two molecules of the chelating ligand, ethylenediamine (en), i.e. among the praseo (green) and violeo (violet) salts of formula $CoCl_3 \cdot 2en$ ²². Jørgensen ascribed the difference in color to *structural* isomerism connected with the linking of the two ethylenediamine molecules, while Werner considered the salts *stereoisomers* – compounds with the same atoms and bonds but differing only in the orientation of these atoms and bonds in space.

If, as Werner insisted, this isomerism were only a geometric consequence of the octahedral structure, it should also be observed among simple tetraammines MA_4B_2 , which do not contain ethylenediamine. However, $[CoCl_2(NH_3)_4]X$ compounds were known in only one series (praseo, green)²³. Jørgensen, a confirmed empiricist, appropriately criticized Werner's theory for implying the existence of unknown compounds. It was only in 1907 that Werner finally prepared the unstable violeo tetraammines, *cis*- $[CoCl_2(NH_3)_4]X$ ²⁴, which are a necessary consequence of his theory but not of Jørgensen's.

Optical isomerism : Although Werner's discovery of violeo salts discredited the Blomstrand-Jørgensen chain theory, Werner's preparation of two – and only two – isomers of $[CoCl_2(NH_3)_4]X$ salts and many other MA_4B_2 compounds was insufficient to prove conclusively his octahedral configuration. In spite of this "negative" evidence, one could argue that failure to isolate a third isomer does not prove its nonexistence. Werner recognized in 1899 that resolving optical isomers of certain types of coordination compounds containing chelate groups (which can span *cis* positions only) could provide the "positive" proof that he sought^{25,26}. After many unsuccessful attempts, he and his American student Victor King (1886–1958) resolved *cis* $[CoClNH_3(en)_2]^{2+}$ salts with silver *d*- α -bromocamphor- π -sulfonate, which proved that cobalt(III) has an octahedral configuration²⁷. In a recent article Ivan Bernal²⁸ has shown that ironically, as a result of conglomerate crystallization (spontaneous resolution), Werner unknowingly had in his possession pure optically active isomers of *cis*- $[Co(NO_2)_2(en)_2]Cl$ in 1901²⁹ (prepared by his first *Doktorandin* and private assistant, the Englishwoman Edith

Humphrey (1875–1977); she lived to the ripe old age of 102!)³⁰, a full decade before Werner and King's resolution of *cis*-[CoClNH₃(en)₂]²⁺ salts and Werner's resolution of *cis*-[Co(NO₂)₂(en)₂]Cl³¹. Therefore, inasmuch as it was the resolution of optically active coordination compounds that brought the coordination theory widespread recognition and Werner the 1913 Nobel Prize in Chemistry³², he might have won the prize earlier than he actually did.

At that time optical activity was almost always connected with carbon atoms, so some of Werner's contemporaries could argue that the optical activity of the numerous mononuclear and polynuclear coordination compounds that he resolved³³ was due to the organic chelate groups present, even though all these symmetrical ligands were optically inactive. Werner's 1914 resolution of completely carbon-free coordination compounds – the tris[tetraammine- μ -dihydroxocobalt(III)]cobalt(III)salts³⁴[Co{(OH)₂Co(NH₃)₄}₃]X₆, first prepared (another irony) by Jørgensen³⁵, finally silenced his opponents. These salts are M(AA)₃ compounds, in which AA is the inorganic bidentate ligand Co(OH)₂(NH₃)₄⁺, and were resolved by another of Werner's *Doktorandinen*, Sophie Matissen.

In his doctoral dissertation (1890)³⁶ Werner had ascribed the geometric isomerism of oximes to the tetrahedral configuration of the nitrogen atom, thus destroying the carbon atoms' monopoly on geometric isomerism. Then, at the peak of his career, he demonstrated that the tetrahedron had no monopoly on optical isomerism, thus attaining a major goal of his career – to prove that stereochemistry is a general phenomenon not limited to carbon compounds and that no fundamental difference exists between organic and inorganic compounds. Werner's structural views were later confirmed by X-ray diffraction studies, as discussed below, but, despite determinations by more *direct* modern techniques, Werner's classical determinations of configuration by simple *indirect* methods remain a monument to his intuitive vision, experimental skill, and inflexible tenacity.

From the inception of his studies of optical activity, Werner did not limit himself to cobalt complexes. He succeeded in resolving coordination compounds of chromium(III), iron(II), rhodium(III), iridium(III) and platinum(IV), which I have discussed elsewhere³³. Near the end of his life he continued his research with cobalt to include complexes with optically active unsymmetrical ligands. For example, he and his assistant A. P. Smirnoff³⁷ resolved *cis*-[Co(NO₂)₂enpn]Br (en = ethylenediamine; pn = propylenediamine); this compound illustrated a new and complicated type of isomerism, which arises from three

causes – (1) *cis* (flavo) geometric isomerism, (2) ligand isomerism ((+)-pn or (-)-pn), and (3) structural isomerism caused by the unsymmetrical nature of the pn ligand (*cis* isomer only). It is a tribute to Werner's octahedral model that he could predict the existence of ten optically active isomers of this complex and a tribute to his experimental skill that he was able to isolate them even though he was unable to assign unambiguous structures to all of them.

In his last article³⁸, published with *Doktorandin* Jeanne Elisabeth Schwyzer and *Doktorand* Walter Karrer, more than a year after his premature death, Werner confirmed his view that β -diketonate anions occupy two coordination positions^{39,40} by resolving optically active salts of the acetylacetonatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) and propionylacetonatobis(ethylenediamine)cobalt(III) cations.

Thus, during his last years Werner devoted himself almost exclusively to the optically active complexes that had proved his stereochemical views and had brought him the Nobel Prize in chemistry. His studies of these complexes underlie much of the more recent and sophisticated studies of the thermodynamics; kinetics; visible, ultraviolet, infrared, NMR, and EPR spectra; rotatory dispersion; circular dichroism; ligand exchange; racemization; absolute configuration; and other aspects of these and similar compounds. Although some of his resolution methods have been improved upon, and his specific rotation values have proved to be too low, he was a true pioneer who first opened a previously unsuspected field.

Alternative theories of coordination compounds

Despite the success of Werner's coordination theory, several twentieth-century chemists, such as the Englishmen John Albert Newton Friend (1881-1966)^{41,42} and Samuel Henry Clifford Briggs (1880-1935)⁴³ and the Russian Georgii Georgievich Povarin (1880-1946)⁴⁴, criticized or modified it and offered alternative explanations for coordination compounds. Even Paul Pfeiffer (1875-1951), Werner's former student, his onetime "chief of staff" at the University of Zurich, and the man who first applied coordination theory to crystal structures, proposed modifications of Werner's theory. In 1920 Pfeiffer applied his principle of "affinity adjustment of the valencies" to answer certain shortcomings of Werner's theory. He considered ionizable radicals or atoms in the outer-sphere as combined with the entire complex radical rather than attached to the central atom or any of its associated molecules, and he applied this idea to organic molecular compounds. His modifications, however, should not be interpreted as attacks on Werner's ideas.

Inner complexes (1904)

With few exceptions, Werner's coordination theory⁹ was accepted by most chemists, and most twentieth-century contributions have been developments, extensions, or confirmations of it rather than ideas incompatible with or opposed to it. One of the earliest of these post-Werner developments is the concept of inner complex salts⁴⁵.

Metal chelates were known in the late nineteenth century, but the first person to recognize clearly the significance and consequences of cyclic structure in coordination compounds was Heinrich Ley (1872-1938), a German chemist. In 1904, using observations of color, transference and distribution experiments, and determinations of molecular weight and electrical conductance, he explained the constitution of copper glycinate and similar compounds. He used Werner's primary valence (*Hauptvalenz*) and secondary valence (*Nebervalenz*) concepts to show that these compounds are not ordinary salts or even ordinary complex salts but a type of metal chelate – an inner metal complex salt (*inneres Metallkomplexsalz*), $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COO})_2]$ (modern, bis(glycinatocopper(II)), in which each chelate ligand is bonded to the central metal ion by both a primary valence (oxygen) and a secondary valence (nitrogen), forming a ring^{45,46}. That same year Giuseppe Bruni and C. Fornara proposed a similar formula for the same compound⁴⁷.

Cyclic bonding and stability : Chugaev's rule of rings (1906)

The rule of rings of the Russian Lev Aleksandrovich Chugaev (1873-1922)⁴⁸ is closely related to Ley's concept of inner complexes. For a molecule with two potential coordinating groups (e.g. a diamine, $\text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{NH}_2$, or an amino acid, $\text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_n\text{COOH}$) to function as a chelate group, it must form a ring of low strain. According to Baeyer's strain theory (1885), 5- and 6-membered rings are the most stable, while 4-membered rings are less stable and 3-membered rings are unstable. In 1906 Chugaev showed that these relationships among organic compounds are applicable to coordination compounds. His rule of rings served as a basis not only for his own stereochemical research but also for that of others, e.g., A. A. Grinberg's method for determining the configuration of Pt^{II} complexes by reaction with oxalic acid (1931)⁴⁹ involves the stability of a 5-membered ring. By comparing the ability of Co^{III} , Ni^{II} and Pt^{II} to form chelates with various diamines, Chugaev also demonstrated the stability of pentatomic and hexatomic ring systems⁵⁰.

Pfeiffer's "crystals as molecular compounds" (1915)

Werner failed to recognize that polynuclear coordination compounds⁵¹ represent a transition between mononuclear complexes and the infinite structure of the crystal lattice. However, Paul Pfeiffer, Paul Niggli, and others reported that crystal structures agree with Werner's coordination theory, as revealed by the new X-ray diffraction technique⁵².

Pfeiffer applied Werner's coordination theory to new areas. He regarded crystals as very high-molecular-weight coordination compounds, in which atoms act as coordination centers, about which further atoms group themselves in specific symmetrical relationships⁵³. He proposed that they obey the structural chemical and steric laws as coordination compounds and that atoms or groups of atoms in crystals are held together by the same chemical forces operating among coordination compounds.

Pfeiffer regarded sodium chloride as a high-molecular-weight coordination compound $(\text{NaCl})_n$ constructed of equal numbers of $[\text{NaCl}_6]$ and $[\text{ClNa}_6]$ units. The difference between primary valences and secondary valences disappears in crystals of symmetrical compounds. He demonstrated that in other crystals, coordination centers can be groups of atoms as well as single atoms and that coordination numbers as high as twelve must sometimes be considered. He proposed that in crystals of simple organic molecular compounds of type AB each constituent acts as a coordination center; AB_6 and BA_6 units interpenetrate exactly as in sodium chloride.

Configurational determination by X-ray diffraction

Wyckoff and Posnjak (1921) : Pfeiffer's application of Werner's theory to crystals and the advent of new experimental techniques led a number of scientists in various countries to use X-ray diffraction to determine crystal structures of coordination compounds. American chemist Ralph W. G. Wyckoff (b. 1897) "chose ammonium hexachloroplatinate(IV) as a crystal that should provide a clear-cut test of Werner coordination"⁵⁴, and, together with Eugen Posnjak (1888-1949), he published the first experimental crystallographic study of a coordination compound⁵⁵. According to Wyckoff, "All six chlorine atoms in $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{PtCl}_6$... were crystallographically identical. They were equally distant from the metal atom, and hence there was no difference in the bonds they formed with it. Furthermore, chlorines were found to be at the corners of a regular octahedron having the platinum atom at its center. A more complete agreement with the predictions of the Werner theory could scarcely have been imagined"⁵⁴.

Other scientists soon used X-ray diffraction to confirm

the octahedral configuration of the six halogen atoms in similar hexacoordinate complexes. Wyckoff also confirmed Werner's view that the molecules of water and of ammonia in most crystalline hydrates and amines are associated with the metallic atom in the same way as the coordinated atoms and radicals in a complex anion. Since the early 1920s, the structures of numerous coordination compounds of various coordination numbers have been determined by X-ray diffraction.

Dickinson (1922) : Less than a year after Wyckoff and Posnjak determined the octahedral configuration for platinum(IV) (coordination number six), American crystallographer Roscoe Gilkey Dickinson (1894-1945) used the same technique to confirm Werner's predicted planar configuration for platinum(II) (coordination number four)⁵⁶. After determining the crystal structure of ammonium hexachlorostannate(IV), $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{SnCl}_6]$ (isomorphous with Wyckoff and Posnjak's $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{PtCl}_6]$), Dickinson determined the crystal structures of potassium tetrachloroplatinate(II), $\text{K}_2[\text{PtCl}_4]$, and potassium and ammonium tetrachloropalladate(II), $\text{K}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ and $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$, and found each platinum or palladium atom to be surrounded by four equivalent and equidistant chlorine atoms in a plane. The ammonia molecules in $[\text{Pt}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{Cl}_2$ show a similar structure.

The crystal structures of numerous other complexes of various coordination numbers have been determined, completely and *directly*, confirming Werner's earlier *indirect* configurational proofs by the preparation and counting of isomers and resolution of optically active compounds. Today the terminology and concepts of coordination chemistry are universally used in crystallography.

Sidgwick's effective atomic number concept (1923)

In 1923 the Englishmen Nevil Vincent Sidgwick (1873-1952) and Thomas Martin Lowry (1874-1936) made the first attempts to interpret Werner's views on an electronic basis. Sidgwick tried to explain coordination number according to the sizes of the sub-groups of electrons in the Bohr atom⁵⁷, and he systematized coordination numbers in his "effective atomic number" (EAN) concept. He regarded ligands as Lewis bases which donate electrons (usually one pair per ligand) to the metal ion, which consequently acts as a Lewis acid. By this process ions add electrons until the EAN (sum of the electrons on the metal ion and the electrons donated by the ligand) of the next noble gas is reached. This EAN rule is now of little theoretical importance. Some elements obey it, but there are many important stable exceptions. However, it is very useful as a predictive rule for

metal carbonyls and nitrosyls. Finally, it is of historical significance in being the result of the first attempt to explain Werner's coordination theory in terms of electronic structure.

Chernyaev's *trans* effect (1926)

Just as substitution reactions in organic chemistry do not occur in a random manner, those among coordination compounds are similarly not random. However, the general principles concerning the directive influences of coordinated ligands were not proposed until the late 1920s; they were deduced from reactions of platinum(II) complexes.

These compounds were among the earliest known complexes. Werner cited the well-known regularities in their substitution reactions to assign *cis* and *trans* configurations to platinum(II) complexes, which he regarded as square-planar⁹. On the basis of their substitution reactions, Werner assigned platosemidiammine chloride (Peyrone's salt) and platosammine chloride (Reiset's second chloride), both with the formula $\text{PtCl}_2(\text{NH}_3)_2$, *cis* and *trans* configurations, respectively. The preparation of both these compounds involves directive influences, the syntheses being known as Peyrone's reaction (exemplifying Peyrone's rule, *cis* orientation) and Jørgensen's reaction (exemplifying Jørgensen's rule, *trans* orientation), respectively (A = NH_3 or an amine; X = a halogen) :

In 1893 Russian chemist Nikolai Semenovitch Kurnakov (1860-1941)⁵⁸ observed a third important regularity⁵⁹. During a study of the substitution of ligands by thiourea and thioacetamide, he found replacement to occur with all the ligands of the *cis* compound but with only the acid radicals of the *trans* compound (A = NH_3 or an amine; X = a halogen or an acid radical, tu = thiourea) :

Because the two isomers yield different products, this reaction (Kurnakov's reaction or Kurnakov's test) has been used to differentiate *cis* from *trans* isomers of platinum(II) or palladium(II)⁶⁰. It was crucial in Werner's proof of the square-planar configuration of Pt^{II} as well as in Chernyaev's formulation of the *trans* effect⁶¹.

Werner recognized the principle of "*trans* elimination" in 1893⁹, but it was only in 1926 that Russian chemist Il'ya Il'ich Chernyaev (1893-1966)⁶²⁻⁶⁴ enunciated his *trans* effect describing the influence of a coordinated ligand on the ease of preparing compounds in which the group *trans* to it

had been replaced⁶¹. According to Chernyaev, a negative group coordinated to a metal atom loosens the bond of any group *trans* to it. Thus Peyrone's, Jørgensen's, and Kurnakov's reactions are all specialized cases of Chernyaev's more general directive influence and are thus explainable by and derivable from it.

Chernyaev also studied substitution reactions of chromium, cobalt, tellurium, and osmium complexes, and he reported that the *trans* effect of atoms is inversely proportional to their metallic character (directly proportional to their electronegativities). Electronegative ligands, e.g. NO_2^- , NCS^- , F^- , Cl^- , Br^- and I^- , have a greater "*trans influence*" than neutral ligands such as NH_3 , amines, or H_2O . His original *trans-directing* series has been extended to include additional ligands: $\text{CN}^- \approx \text{CO} \blacktriangleright \text{C}_2\text{H}_4 \blacktriangleright \text{NO} > \text{CH}_3 \blacktriangleright \text{SC}(\text{NH}_2)_2 \blacktriangleright \text{SR}_2 \blacktriangleright \text{PR}_3 > \text{SO}_3\text{H}^- > \text{NO}_2^- \blacktriangleright \text{I}^- \blacktriangleright \text{SCN}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^- > \text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N} > \text{RNH}_2 \blacktriangleright \text{NH}_3 > \text{OH}^- > \text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Proof of the square-planar configuration for platinum(II)

As we have seen earlier, the octahedral configuration of cobalt(III) and platinum(IV) (coordination number six) was proven in three ways: (1) chemical evidence such as "isomer counting" and transformation reactions, (2) resolution of selected compounds, and (3) X-ray diffraction studies. The first two methods were pursued successfully largely by Werner.

The square-planar configuration of platinum(II) was proven by the same methods but with a later chronology and a difference in interpretation of the resolutions. Three symmetrical configurations for coordination number four are theoretically possible: tetrahedral, square-planar, and square-pyramidal. Because only few platinum(II) and palladium(II) isomers were known and similar isomerism among other elements was not discovered for a number of years, Werner's square-planar configuration (1893)⁹ was questioned more and more strongly as time went by, and other evidence was proposed to account for the structures of these compounds. For example, several workers claimed to have isolated more than two isomers for compounds of type MA_2B_2 , which would eliminate a square-planar configuration although it is also not compatible with either the tetrahedral or square-pyramidal arrangements. Also, others claimed to have resolved tetracoordinate platinum(II) complexes of type $\text{M}(\text{AB})_2$, a fact inexplicable by the square-planar configuration.

Dickinson's X-ray diffraction proof of a square-planar arrangement of chloride ions around the central metal atoms in $\text{K}_2[\text{PtCl}_4]$, $\text{K}_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$, and $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{PdCl}_4]$ was confirmed

by additional X-ray structural studies of other compounds. Linus Pauling explained the square-planar structure of platinum(II) and palladium(II) compounds on a theoretical basis and predicted a similar configuration for diamagnetic compounds of nickel(II), gold(III), copper(III), and silver(III)⁶⁵.

In 1928 Chernyaev used his *trans* effect to confirm the square-planar configuration for platinum(II) by preparing the three theoretically possible geometric isomers of $[\text{Pt}(\text{NO}_2)(\text{NH}_3)(\text{NH}_2\text{OH})(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N})]\text{Cl}$, i.e. a compound of type MABCD⁶⁶. The occurrence of three geometric isomers eliminated the tetrahedral arrangement but did not absolutely rule out the square-pyramidal configuration. It could still be argued that each of Chernyaev's isomers consists of an asymmetric pair but that he was unable to resolve them. Because it is impossible to prove a negative proposition, another problem of "negative" evidence similar to that which Werner had faced earlier had again arisen.

In 1934 and 1937 English chemist Harry D. K. Drew *et al.*⁶⁷ tried to solve the problem by preparing isomers of compound types $\text{M}(\text{AA})\text{CD}$ and $\text{M}(\text{AB})\text{CD}$. For the symmetrical chelate group he chose ethylenediamine and for the unsymmetrical one, isobutylenediamine (1,2-diamino-2-methylpropane). For the first type complex he obtained one and only one form, whereas for the second type complex he obtained two geometric isomers. His experimental data agree with the square-planar configuration; he did not consider the square-pyramidal configuration.

As Werner, a generation before, had realized that successful resolution of coordination compounds would offer a "positive" proof that hexacoordinate cobalt(III) possesses an octahedral configuration, English chemist William Hobson Mills (1873-1959) realized that resolution of a certain type of bisbidentate complex of platinum(II) would permit a definite decision to be made between the planar and tetrahedral configurations. In 1935, a date within the lifetime of many of us here today, Mills, together with Thomas H. H. Quibell, prepared dichloro(1,2-diamino-2-methylpropane) platinum(II) by the reaction of isobutylenediamine with potassium tetrachloroplatinate(II)⁶⁸. By reacting *meso*-1,2-diphenylethylenediamine (stilbenediamine) with this compound they obtained 1,2-diamino-2-methylpropane (*meso*-1,2-diamino-1,2-diphenylethane)-platinum(II) chloride. If the arrangement of the bonds around the platinum atom in this compound were tetrahedral, the chelate rings would lie in planes perpendicular to each other, a configuration with a median plane of symmetry which could not give rise to optical isomerism. However, if the two chelate rings were coplanar, the cation would be disymmetric, and optical

isomerism would be possible.

Mills and Quibell resolved this compound into stable enantiomorphs using diacetyl-*d*-tartaric anhydride as the resolving agent. Because simple complexes such as $[\text{Pt}(\text{bn})(\text{en})]\text{Cl}_2$ (en = ethylenediamine; bn = isobutylenediamine) have never been resolved, there is no evidence favoring the square-pyramidal configuration. Mills and Quibell's resolution eliminated the tetrahedral configuration and offered unequivocal proof for the planar configuration of platinum(II). In 1939 Lidstone and Mills resolved the corresponding palladium(II) compound by the same method⁶⁹. By this time other stereochemical and crystallographic evidence for the configuration of platinum(II) and palladium(II) existed, but Mills' resolutions afforded ingenious, elegant, and entirely independent proofs.

Other developments

In his 1965 book *History of the Concept of Valency to 1930*, W. G. Palmer stated that it is "yet too early to assess the very rapid developments since 1930 in a just historical perspective". The same may be said about coordination chemistry. For this reason and because of space limitations, my detailed historical account of coordination chemistry during the twentieth century must close at this point. In general, reasearch, discoveries, and innovations in the field since the 1930s have taken place at an ever-accelerating rate.

Despite the guiding star of Werner's coordination theory, classical coordination chemistry was largely empirical. Modern coordination chemistry has been characterized by increased emphasis on comprehensive theories of chemical bonding that have served to integrate and explain the large amount of experimental data. The valence bond (VB) theory of coordination was developed by Linus Pauling and John C. Slater from Gilbert Newton Lewis' covalent model (1916). Closely related to theories of hybridization and resonance, this theory was the first successful application of the electronic theory of valence to coordination compounds. From the early 1930s to the early 1950s virtually all coordination phenomena were interpreted in its terms. It gave simple and satisfactory answers to geometric and magnetic susceptibility questions, with which chemists were then concerned.

Walther Kossel's ionic model (1916) was revitalized and developed into the crystal field theory (CFT) of coordination by Hans Bethe and John H. Van Vleck. Although used to some extent by physicists as early as the 1930s, it was not generally accepted by chemists until the 1950s. When modified to include some degree of covalence, crystal field theory is usually known as ligand field theory (LFT) or ad-

justed crystal field theory (ACFT) and is currently the best and most popular method for treating spectra and other properties quantitatively. A simpler electrostatic theory is the valence-shell electron-pair repulsion (VSEPR) theory of directed valency, proposed in 1957 by Ronald J. Gillespie and the late Ronald S. Nyholm. Both VB theory and CFT are only simplifications of the more general but more complicated molecular orbital (MO) theory, which today offer the best interpretation of the properties of coordination compounds. In the future these theories will probably be modified, or even totally new ones may arise.

Another characteristic of modern coordination chemistry is the increasing reliance upon physicochemical methods unknown to Werner and his contemporaries. Simultaneously with an introduction of these newer techniques, emphasis shifted from preoccupation with *qualitative* studies of structure and stereochemistry to *quantitative* studies of thermodynamics, kinetics and reaction mechanisms. Some areas of current research interest include unusual ligands, oxidation states, and coordination number; solid state chemistry; photochemistry; relationship between structure and reactivity; variable oxidation state; chelates; heteropoly complexes; organometallic compounds such as metallocenes and π -aromatic complexes with "sandwich structures"; compounds with metal-metal bonds (metal clusters); clathrates; fluxional coordination compounds; borane complexes; macrocyclic and stereochemically nonrigid ligands; and nitrogen- and oxygen-containing complexes. Many biologically active compounds are complexes, and even the simpler types of complexes have served as model compounds in investigating bodily processes. In fact, the new field of bioinorganic chemistry is concerned largely with coordination compounds.

The following chronological list of some historically significant events in coordination chemistry is intended to supplement the previous more detailed historical survey. It is necessarily incomplete, for many other valuable contributions have not been included because of lack of space.

Some historically significant events in twentieth-century coordination chemistry

- | | |
|------|--|
| 1900 | W. J. Pope and S. J. Peachey, Resolution of optically active tin compound (tetrahedral $\text{MeETPrSn}^+\text{X}^-$) |
| 1904 | A. Werner, <i>Lehrbuch der Stereochemie</i> |
| 1905 | A. Werner, <i>Neuere Anschauungen auf dem Gebiete der anorganischen Chemie</i> |
| 1905 | L. A. Chugaev, Dimethylglyoximate test for nickel (first organic spot test reagent for a metal ion) |

- 1905 H. Grossmann, Use of high ionic strength medium for studying complex constants
- 1906 H. Copaux, Classification of iso- and heteropoly compounds
- 1907 L. A. Chugaev and V. Sokolov, First coordination compound containing an asymmetric ligand; stereospecificity
- 1908 M. Delépine, Metal dithiocarbamates
- 1908-17 A. Miolati and A. Rosenheim, Classification and structural theory of isopoly and heteropoly compounds
- 1910 F. Challenger and F. S. Kipping, Resolution of optically active tetrahedral $R_1R_2R_3R_4Si$
- 1913 A. Werner, Nobel Prize in Chemistry "for his work on the linkage of atoms in molecules..."
- 1915 L. A. Chugaev and N. A. Vladimirov, Chugaev's salt, $[PtCl(NH_3)_5]Cl_3$
- 1916 W. Kossel, First calculation of energy of a complex by electrostatic model
- 1918 H. Hürlimann, Stereospecificity
- 1919 F. Hein, First arene complex
- 1919 F. Feigl, First cage complex
- 1921 G. J. Burrows and E. E. Turner, Resolution of optically active arsenic compound (tetrahedral $R_1R_2R_3As^+X^-$)
- 1921 M. Delépine, Active recemates
- 1925 P. Job, Determination of stability constants by method by continuous variations
- 1926 J. N. Brønsted, S_N1CB mechanism (substitution, nucleophilic, first order, conjugate base)
- 1926 W. H. Mills and R. A. Gotts, Resolution of optically active beryllium compound (tetrahedral bis(benzoylpyruvato)beryllium(II))
- 1927 H. de Diesbach and E. von der Weid, First metal phthalocyanine
- 1927-31 E. U. Condon, W. Heitler, F. London, L. Pauling and J. C. Slater, Valence bond theory and orbital hybridization
- 1929 T. M. Lowry and F. L. Gilbert, Resolution of optically active tellurium compound (tetrahedral $R_1R_2R_3Te^+X^-$)
- 1929-32 H. Bethe, R. S. Mulliken and J. H. Van Vleck, Crystal field theory (ligand field theory)
- 1931 R. Scharz and M. Lewinson, Resolution of optically active germanium compound (tetrahedral $PhEtPrGe^+Br^-$)
- 1931 H. Reihlen and W. Hühn, Claimed of optically active palladium(IV) and platinum(IV) compounds as evidence for a tetrahedral configuration (never confirmed)
- 1931 P. Pfeiffer, The Pfeiffer effect
- 1932 J. Bjerrum, Square-pyramidal $[Cu(NH_3)_5]^{2+}$
- 1933 P. Pfeiffer, E. Breith, E. Lubbe and T. Tsumaki, Oxygen-carrying chelate, bis(salicylal)ethylenediiminecobalt(II)
- 1933 F. G. Mann, Resolution of Na *cis*- $[Rh\{SO_2(NH_2)_2\}_2(H_2O)_2]$ (second completely inorganic coordination compound to be resolved)
- 1934 J. C. Bailar, Jr. and R. W. Auten, Optical inversion in reactions of cobalt complexes (inorganic Walden inversion)
- 1934 R. P. Linstead, Iron(II) and copper(II) phthalocyanines
- 1935 C. Brosset, Structure of $K_3W_2Cl_9$ (metal-metal bonds)
- 1935 K. A. Jensen, Dipole moments to determine structures of Pt^{II} isomers
- 1937 H. A. Jahn and E. Teller, Jahn-Teller effect
- 1938 T. Tsumaki, Explanation of oxygen-carrying chelates
- 1938 M. Calvin, Hydrogenation of benzoquinone by copper(I) acetate (first homogeneous catalytic process)
- 1938 R. Tsuchida, Spectrochemical series of ligands
- 1939 L. Pauling, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond"
- 1940 J. H. Van Vleck and R. Finkelstein, First application of electrostatic model to absorption bands of the ruby
- 1940 N. V. Sidgwick and H. M. Powell, Nonbonding pairs of electrons and stereochemistry
- 1941 J. Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution : Theory of the Reversible Step Reactions"
- 1943 P. Ray and N. K. Dutt, Tetragonal twist mechanism
- 1944 A. Zinke and E. Ziegler, First calixarenes
- 1945-49 C. Brosset, Structures of $Mo_6Cl_8^{4+}$ compounds (metal-metal bonds)
- 1946 G. Schwarzenbach, Ethylenediaminetetraacetate (EDTA) in complexometric titrations
- 1948 H. Irving and R. J. P. Williams, Stability order of complexes

- 1950 J. Chatt and R. G. Williams, $\text{Pt}(\text{C}^2\text{H}^4)_2\text{Cl}_2$ (first example of two double bonds on one metal atom)
- 1950 F. P. Dwyer and F. Lions, Resolution of hexadentate chelate complex with molecular rotation of more than 50000° (1,8-bis(salicylideneamino)-3,6-dithiaoctanecobalt(III) cation)
- 1950 J. Chatt, Symposium on Coordination Chemistry (1st International Conference on Coordination Chemistry), Welwyn, England
- 1951 J. W. Irvine, Jr. and G. Wilkinson, $[\text{Ni}_9\text{PX}_3]_4$ (where X = F, Cl or Br)
- 1951 M. J. S. Dewar, π -bonding in metal-olefin complexes
- 1951-52 T. J. Kealey and P. L. Pauson (1951); S. A. Miller, J. A. Tebboth and J. F. Tremaine (1952), Discovery of biscyclopentadienyliron(II), later called ferrocene
- 1952 R. B. Woodward, G. Wilkinson, M. Rosenblum and M. C. Whiting, Recognition of structure and aromatic properties of biscyclopentadienyliron(II); named it "ferrocene"
- 1952 H. Taube, Inner and outer orbital complexes (labile and inert)
- 1952 G. Schwarzenbach, The chelate effect
- 1952 M. Wolfsberg and L. Helmholz, Molecular orbital model applied to transition metal complexes
- 1954 Y. Tanabe and S. Sugano, Calculation of energy level diagrams for octahedral *d*-group complexes
- 1954 G. Wilkinson, Lanthanum cyclopentadienides
- 1954 E. O. Fischer, "Metal Complexes of Cyclopentadienes and Indenes (*Habilitationsschrift*)"
- 1955 E. O. Fischer and W. Hafner, Bisbenzenechromium(0)
- 1955 J. M. Birmingham and G. Wilkinson, Biscyclopentadienylrhenium hydride (homogeneous catalyst and first noncarbonyl metal hydride)
- 1955 Y. Saito, K. Nakatsu, M. Shiro and H. Kuroya, Absolute configuration of D- and L- $[\text{Co}(\text{en})_3]^{3+}$
- 1955 J. Chatt, L. A. Duncanson and L. M. Venanzi; L. E. Orgel, π -Bonding theory of the *trans* effect
- 1955 F. P. Dwyer, E. C. Gyarfás and D. P. Mellor, Resolution of complex with hexadentate ligand ($[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$)
- 1956 L. N. Essen and A. D. Gel'man, Synthesis of $[\text{Pt}(\text{Br})(\text{I})(\text{NO}_2)(\text{Cl})(\text{NH}_3)(\text{py})]$ (only example of MABCDEF)
- 1956 D. C. Hodgkin, Crystal structure of the cobalt(III) complex of vitamin B₁₂
- 1957 J. Bobinski, M. Fein and N. Mayes, 1-Isopropenylcarborane (first published carborane; E. L. Muetterties had previously synthesized carboranes in classified rocket fuel research)
- 1957 J. Chatt, R. Duncanson, and B. L. Shaw, $[\text{PtHCl}\{(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}\}_2]$ (homogeneous catalyst)
- 1957 G. Schwarzenbach and L. G. Sillen, "Stability Constants of Metal-Ion Complexes"
- 1958 C. E. Schaffer and C. K. Jørgensen, Nephelauxetic series (interelectronic repulsion) of central atoms and ligands
- 1958 S. Ahrland, J. Chatt and N. R. Davies, Systematization of donor atom coordination tendencies of metal ions
- 1958 J. C. Bailar, Jr., Trigonal twist mechanism
- 1959 J. Chatt, Electronic conditions for stability of organometallic compounds
- 1959 F. G. A. Stone, First cyclooctatetraene complexes
- 1959 L. H. Sommer, First resolution of optically active silicon compounds
- 1959 E. J. Corey and J. C. Bailar, Jr., Conformational analysis of coordination compounds
- 1959 W. H. Zachariasen and H. A. Plettinger, Hexagonal bipyramidal 8-coordination, $[\text{UO}_2(\text{OCOCH}_3)_3]^-$
- 1960 A. R. Pitochelli and M. F. Hawthorne, Icosahedral $[\text{B}_{12}\text{H}_{12}]^{2-}$
- 1960 S. Kirschner, Resolution and structure-proof of a hexacoordinate silicon complex
- 1960 R. B. Woodward *et al.*, Proof of structure of chlorophyll by total synthesis
- 1960 R. A. Marcus, Outer sphere electron transfer theory
- 1960 E. Wasserman, First catenane (interlocking carbocyclic rings; from Latin, *catena*, chain)
- 1960-67 J. C. Bailar, Jr., M. J. S. Crespi and J. Geldard, Action of biological systems on optically active complexes
- 1961 C. K. Jørgensen, Optical electronegativities from electron transfer spectra

- 1962 R. E. Sievers, R. W. Moshier and M. L. Morris, Resolution of chromium hexafluoride acetylacetonate by gas chromatography
- 1962 N. Bartlett, Synthesis of $\text{Xe}[\text{PtF}_6]$
- 1962 F. Basolo and G. S. Hamaker, Linkage isomerism, nitritopentaammines of Rh^{III} , Ir^{III} , and Pt^{IV}
- 1962-65 D. H. Busch *et al.*, Molecular template concept; kinetic and thermodynamic template effects; organizing and closing of macrocycles and macrobicycles
- 1963 L. Vaska, Reversible reaction of $[\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})\{(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}\}_2]$ with molecular oxygen
- 1963 L. F. Dahl *et al.*, First metal carbonyl containing a metal cluster
- 1963 J. A. Bertrand, F. A. Cotton and W. A. Dollase; W. T. Robinson, J. E. Fergusson and B. R. Penfold, Structure of triangular $[\text{Re}_3\text{Cl}_{12}]^{3-}$ anion (metal-metal multiple bonds)
- 1963 R. G. Pearson, Hard and soft acids and bases
- 1963 K. Ziegler and G. Natta, Nobel Prize in Chemistry "for their discovery of the chemistry and technology of high polymers" (homogeneous catalysis)
- 1964 F. A. Cotton and C. B. Harris, Binuclear metal clusters, $[\text{Re}_2\text{C}_{18}]^{2-}$ (quadruple bonds)
- 1964 S. C. Abrahams, A. P. Ginsberg and K. Knox, K^2ReH^9 (homogeneous catalyst)
- 1965 B. Rosenberg, L. Van Camp, and T. Krigas, Biological effects of platinum complexes ("cisplatin")
- 1965 R. Eisenberg and J. A. Ibers, Tris(*cis*-1,2-diphenylethylene-1,2-dithiolato)rhenium, $\text{Re}(\text{S}^2\text{C}^2(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2)_3$ (trigonal prismatic coordination)
- 1965 A. D. Allen and C. V. Senoff, First metal complex with molecular nitrogen
- 1965 C. H. Langford and H. B. Gray, π -Bonding theory of the *trans* effect
- 1965 H. Taube, Proof of inner sphere mechanism : $[\text{CoCl}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{2+} + \text{Cr}^{2+} \rightarrow [\text{CrCl}(\text{NH}_3)_5]^{2+} + \text{Co}^{2+}$
- 1965 D. L. Kepert, Calculations of shapes of hexacoordinate complexes
- 1965 I. I. Chernyaev, L. S. Korablina and G. S. Muraveiskaya, Optically active complexes with only unidentate ligands
- 1965 M. F. Hawthorne, D. C. Young and P. A. Wegner, First metallocarborane
- 1966 G. Wilkinson, Homogeneous hydrogenation of olefins by $\{(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}\}_3\text{RhCl}$ (Wilkinson's catalyst)
- 1967 J. M. Williams, Hydrated proton $[\text{H}_5\text{O}_2]^+$ in $[\text{CoCl}_2(\text{en})_2]\text{Cl.HCl.H}_2\text{O}$
- 1967 F. Basolo and R. G. Pearson, "Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions"
- 1967 C. J. Pedersen, First crown ether (complexes with planar, macrocyclic ligands)
- 1967 J. A. Ibers and D. J. Hodgson, Structure of $[\text{Ir}(\text{NO})(\text{CO})\{(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}\}_2\text{Cl}]^+$ showing bent M-NO-bond
- 1967 M. Eigen, Nobel Prize in Chemistry "for...studies of extremely fast reactions..."
- 1968 D. R. Boston and N. J. Bose, Cage compounds (bicyclic ligands encapsulating metal ions)
- 1968 A. Streitwieser, Jr. and U. Muller-Westerhoff, Bis(cyclooctatetraene)uranium(IV), in which π -molecular orbitals share electrons with uranium *f*-orbitals
- 1968 D. R. Boston and N. J. Bose, Clathrochelates
- 1969 D. K. Cabbiness and D. W. Margerum, Recognition and naming of the macrocyclic effect
- 1969 J. P. Fackler, Jr., K. Knox, D. Couvouvani, *et al.*, Cubic 8-coordination
- 1969 D. Brown, J. F. Easey and C. E. F. Rickard, Cubic 8-coordination, $\text{Na}_3[\text{PaF}_8]$
- 1970 D. A. Owen and M. F. Hawthorne, Carborane-transition metal chelate complexes
- 1971 R. Countryman and W. S. McDonald, Cubic 8-coordination, $[\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_4][\text{U}(\text{SCN})_8]$
- 1971 H. B. Gray *et al.*, Electronic structures of polynuclear forms of biological iron
- 1971-74 P. W. R. Confield and P. G. Eller (1971); P. H. Davis, R. L. Belford and I. C. Paul (1973); N. C. Baenziger, K. M. Dittmore and J. R. Doyle (1974); J. A. Tiethof, A. T. Hetey and D. W. Meek (1974), Planar 3-coordination, $\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{PS}\}_3\text{Cu}[\text{ClO}_4]$, $\{(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}\}_2\text{CuBr}$, $\{(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}\}_2\text{AuCl}$, and $\{(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{PS}\}_3\text{Cu}$
- 1972 E. L. Amma *et al.*, 3-Coordinate copper ($[\text{Cu}(\text{ethylenethiourea})_3]_2\text{SO}_4$)
- 1973 J. P. Collman and S. R. Winter, First stable formyl complex, $(\text{CO})_4\text{Fe}(\text{CHO})^-$
- 1973 G. L. Simon and L. F. Dahl, First "naked" phosphorus complex

- 1973 E. O. Fischer and G. Wilkinson, Nobel Prize in Chemistry "for their pioneering work...on the chemistry of...sandwich compounds"
- 1973 J. M. Lehn, Supramolecular chemistry; D. J. Cram, Host-guest complexation
- 1974 J. P. Collman *et al.*, Picket fence porphyrin
- 1974 J. L. Dye *et al.*, Cryptated sodium cation and anion
- 1974 L. F. Dahl, Platinum carbonyl cluster dianions ("tinker toy" construction) with trigonal prismatic configuration
- 1974 H. B. Gray, Replacement experiments on blue copper proteins
- 1975 C. M. Lukehart, G. P. Torrence and J. V. Zerle, Diacetylmethylate anions
- 1975 L. Horner, H. Kunz and P. Walach, First tetraphosphine macrocycle
- 1974-75 N. J. de Stephano, D. K. Johnson and L. M. Venanzi (1974); I. Mochida, J. A. Mattern and J. C. Bailar, Jr. (1975), *Trans*-spanning ligands in planar complexes
- 1976 E. C. Baker *et al.*, Lanthanide and actinide organometallics (preceded about a decade earlier by E. L. Muetterties' unpublished work at DuPont)
- 1976 L. D. Lower and L. F. Dahl, $\text{Ni}_8(\text{CO})_8\{(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}\}_6$, (cube-shaped metal cluster compound, the first transition metal analogue of cubane)
- 1976-83 I. Tabushi, Y. Murakami, *et al.*, Cyclophanes (a new family of receptor)
- 1977 A. M. Sargeson *et al.*, First "sepulchrate" (polyaza macrobicycles analogous to cryptates)
- 1977-83 R. H. Holm, Iron-sulfur proteins, $[\text{4Fe-4S}]^{n+}$ clusters
- 1978 C. D. Gutsche and R. J. Muthukrishnan, Calixarenes
- 1978 R. D. Gillard and F. L. Wimmer, Third resolution of a completely inorganic complex, $[\text{Pt}(\text{S}_5)_3]^{2-}$
- 1979 D. H. Busch *et al.*, Cyclidenes (lacunar ligands, a series of bicyclic macrocycles)
- 1979 S. Shimba, S. Fujinami and M. Shibata, Fourth and fifth resolutions of completely inorganic complexes, *cis-cis-cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{CN})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$ and *cis-cis-cis*- $[\text{Co}(\text{NO}_2)_2(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^+$
- 1980 M. Åelap, Resolution of $\text{W}(\text{OCOC}_5\text{H}_4\text{N})_2$ -
($\text{ONC}_9\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$)₂, the first resolution of an 8-coordinate compound
- 1982 H. B. Gray *et al.*, Protein electron-transfer rate over long and fixed distance (pentaammine-ruthenium(III)(histidine-33)ferricytochrome c)
- 1983 H. Taube, Nobel Prize in Chemistry "for his work on the mechanisms of electron transfer reactions, especially in metal complexes"
- 1987 D. J. Cram, J. -M. Lehn and C. J. Pedersen "for their development and use of molecules with structure-specific interactions of high selectivity"
- 1990 G. L. Eichorn, Bonding of metal ions to DNA
- 1991 P. J. Fagan, J. C. Calabrese and B. Malone, $\{(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_3\text{P}\}_2\text{Pt}(\eta\text{-C}_{60})$, first complex in which a fullerene acts as ligand toward a metal atom
- 1994-95 J. Rebek, Jr. *et al.*, Self-replicating molecules
- 1995 G. M. Whitesides *et al.*, Hydrogen-bonding effects in design of templates
- 1995 M. Fujita; P. Stang, Metal ion interlocked structures
- 1995-96 H. B. Gray *et al.*, Electron-transfer and tunneling in proteins
- 1996 J. K. M. Sanders *et al.*, Ligands as anchors in coordination templates
- 1996-97 J. P. Sauvage; J. F. Stoddart, Catenanes and knots; interlocked structures
- 1997 C. Piguet, G. Bernardinelli and G. Hopfgartner, Multisite double and triple helical complexes
- 1997 B. Linton and A. D. Hamilton, Artificial receptors by metal-templated processes

Conclusion

As we have seen, in his last works Werner stood on the threshold of an extremely complicated area of research – the study of optically active coordination compounds containing optically active ligands. Had the powerful, creative trend of his life not been cut short by his untimely death at the age of 53, there is no telling what he might have accomplished in this field. Just as the founder of coordination chemistry would have been amazed by the discoveries made since his death, so will we likely be amazed by the discoveries to be made in the next century. It is difficult if not impossible to predict the future of coordination chemistry, an exciting research field in which the solution to any given problem usually opens up a number of new research avenues and poses newer and more challenging problems. If its past history gives any indication of its future course, the continued success,

expansion, and vitality of coordination chemistry remain assured.

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